

Hubble Space Telescope Observations of the Recent
Evolution of SN 1987A

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Abstract

The unusual structure and unique evolution of Supernova 1987A make this stellar remnant a subject of great interest for astrophysicists. Over the past 25 years researchers have observed a dynamic interaction unfold between its three circumstellar rings, the shock wave produced in the initial explosion, and the explosion debris itself. In collaboration with the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics and NASA's SAINTS observing program, the author gained access to the most recent unpublished *Hubble Space*

Telescope (HST) images of SN 1987A in both the B and R optical bands. Close examination of these images in both DS9 and IRAF indicates a decrease of approximately 20% in the luminosity of the 29 "hot spots" which line the inner ring as well as a brightening by 40% along its southeastern edge. While a compact point source at the remnant's center has yet to be detected, comparison of the 2011 and 2013 HST data using a point spread function reveals a 10% decrease in the upper limit on its luminosity from 4.4×10^{32} ergs/s in 2011 to 4.0×10^{32} ergs/s in 2013.

Introduction

Supernova 1987A was the brightest supernova to be observed from Earth since Johannes Kepler witnessed the explosion of SN 1604 in our own Milky Way Galaxy. The supernova's progenitor star, Sanduleak 69-202, was a blue supergiant in the nearby Large Magellanic Cloud, a dwarf galaxy located approximately 51.4 kiloparsecs from Earth. The galaxy's declination of -69° makes it most visible from the Southern Hemisphere, where astronomers at

the Las Campanas Observatory in northern Chile first observed the star's explosion with the naked eye on the night of February 24, 1987. The early detection of SN 1987A and the existence of archival photographic plates of its progenitor make this event the first time astronomers have been able to actively chart the full evolution of a supernova from progenitor to remnant.

Figure 1 depicts an optical image of SN 1987A taken by the HST Advanced Camera for Surveys on December 6, 2006. The supernova system consists of the central remnant of

Figure 1: Hubble Space Telescope: NASA/ESA/P.Challis & R.Kirshner (CfA), Dec 6, 2006

Sanduleak 69-202, its three circumstellar rings, and the expanding debris from the explosion. The two outer rings appear roughly equidistant from the center of the system, while the third is much smaller and closer to the center, forming an hourglass figure around the explosion site. The two bright points of light at the edge of the system are neighboring stars.

Archival photographs of the progenitor star Sanduleak 69-202 indicate that it was a blue supergiant at the time of explosion, which contradicts the

long-held belief that Type II supernovae only form from red supergiants (Fransson et al., 2007). One possible explanation for SN 1987A atypical progenitor is that the star was in fact a red supergiant at one point, expelling much of its outer hydrogen envelope into the surrounding circumstellar medium as it continued to expand. However, about 20,000 years ago the star underwent a highly unusual evolution into a blue supergiant, perhaps due to internal structural changes resulting from the unusually low metallicity of the Large Magellanic Cloud (Fransson et al., 2007). The solar wind resulting from this evolution would have expanded outward at a much more rapid rate than the original wind produced during the star's red supergiant phase. The primary wind was therefore caught up in the secondary wind from the blue supergiant phase at the boundary of a nearby H-II region, resulting in the unusual hourglass shape we see today (Pasachoff & Filippenko, 2007).

The non-spherical explosion and three-ring structure of SN 1987A are unlike anything before observed in a Type II supernova of this size. Older supernovae such as the Crab Nebula or SN 1604 ('Kepler's Supernova') display

a spherical shell – not a ring – of luminous debris which envelopes a compact neutron star or black hole in a generally uniform fashion. The remnant's three-ring structure as well as the asymmetrical brightening and spot formation along SN 1987A's inner ring significantly diverge from this spherical model of supernova expansion. However, it is important to recall that SN 1987A is in many ways the first of its kind: older supernovae like the Crab Nebula were never observed at such an early evolutionary stage, nor with such precision and detail. In fact, with no other basis for comparison, it is entirely possible that the unusual structure and brightening of SN 1987A are actually quite typical for the earliest stages of Type II supernovae evolution.

The first bright spots along the inner ring appeared about 4000 days after the initial explosion was observed. Several more spots continued to appear over the next eight years, first along the ring's western half then progressing steadily eastwards, until they spanned its full diameter. This unusual west-east brightening pattern is attributed to either an asymmetrical explosion (Michael et al., 2000) or to the 45° tilt of the supernova system with

respect to the Earth, which would cause light from the half of the ring tilted closer to the Earth to become visible earlier than light from its farther side (Wang et al., 2002). High N/C ratios in the circumstellar material of the inner ring confirm its origin in CNO processing inside the progenitor star (Fransson et al., 1989), but the origins of the two outer rings are still not fully understood.

Observations and Analysis

This paper represents a close examination of the most recent images from 2013 received as part of the HST observing program for SN 1987A at the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics. The full data set consisted of 311 unpublished images in the optical B and R bands, taken with HST's Wide Field Camera 3 (WFC3) 2013 at an angular resolution of less than one arcsecond. The goals of this project were to 1) record any change in luminosity of the hot spots along the equatorial ring; 2) monitor the

expansion of the ejecta material; and 3) determine a more stringent upper limit on a point source of light at the center of the supernova remnant.

The change in luminosity for the 2013 images was determined through comparison with the 2011 images in the program DS9. A simple flux subtraction revealed the changes over the past two years across a range of images. I then compared the most recent luminosity values with the values recorded for each hot spot by HST's three optical cameras from 1994 to 2013 in a graph and in a time lapse film in order to achieve a clearer picture of the impact of these most recent images on the supernova's evolutionary history overall.

In 2012 Dom Pesce at Harvard established an optical upper limit of 1.6

$\times 10^{33}$ ergs/s for a point source within

the remnant by applying a point source function (PSF) to HST WFC2 images

from 2011. PSF analysis involves generating several versions of the same

Figure 2: PSF data in order of increasing magnitude (15.0-19.9)

image in which a star of varying magnitudes has been artificially introduced through the program IRAF using a point spread function. An unbiased subject can then view these images to determine whether or not a star is visible; the magnitude at which the star becomes visible is taken to be the upper limit on the source.

I first attempted to replicate Pesce's findings for 2011 using the same point source function before applying it to the 2013 images. Figure 3 depicts 50 duplicates of the same 2013 WFC3 image, each containing a false star of magnitude 15.0 to 19.9 and separated by increments of 0.1. While Pesce ran this test on several individuals viewing randomized images, the results of this paper are based only on my own subjective viewing of the images, although I was blinded to the true magnitude of the false star.

Results

Comparisons between the most recent HST images and the 2011 images using flux subtraction indicate a decrease

Figure 3: Flux subtraction image, 2011-2013. Black = decrease, white = increase

in luminosity across all 29 spots averaging

approximately 20%. However, the subtraction technique also revealed an unexpected increase in luminosity along the southwestern edge of the ring

(bottom right quadrant) of approximately 40%. This edge is visible as a

prominent white lining along

the inner ring in Figure 3.

Note that this image shows

no change in the outer rings,

which are indiscernible from

the image background.

A comparative graph of the R-band luminosity for each spot from 1994 to present day confirms this overall decrease in luminosity (Figure 4). The

darker lines represent spots on the eastern half of the ring, and the lighter lines represent their counterparts on the western half. The east-west progression of the spots is actually quite visible, with what appear to be two distinct groups peaking near days 7000 and 8000 respectively. While it is impossible to draw conclusions about the origins of the spots' asymmetry, the apparent synchronization of these two groups suggests a topic for further research that may shed more light on this question.

The point source estimate obtained using the false star PSF method fell from 4.4×10^{32} ergs/s in 2011 to 4.0×10^{32} ergs/s in 2013, indicating a decrease of 10% in the upper limit for the luminosity of a point source at the center of the SN 1987A system. These values are much smaller than previous estimates, which placed the upper limit between 1.6×10^{33} ergs/s (Pesce, 2012) and 5×10^{33} ergs/s (Graves et al., 2005). In fact, my value for 2011 is actually less than Pesce's by a factor of ten. The disconnect between the 2011 values obtained in my and Pesce's research indicates that the calibration of these frames – both Pesce's and my own – is far from absolute, and requires

further analysis before more conclusions can be made. However, despite this disagreement the improvement in the upper limit from 2011 to 2013 remains unaffected. The 2013 upper limit is 10% more stringent than the limit found using the same methods for 2011, and so the point source remains elusive.

Discussion

Stellar evolutionary theory predicts that the collapse of a massive star like Sanduleak 69-202 into a supernova releases 99% of its energy in the form of neutrinos, which travel at a velocity approaching the speed of light (Pasachoff & Filippenko, 2007). Solar neutrino detectors in Ohio, Russia and Japan set up to monitor solar neutrinos indeed registered a total of 24 a few hours prior to the first sighting of the explosion in Chile, confirming theoretical models of core collapse supernovae processes. Neutrinos are not visible to the human eye, so astronomers believe that the six-magnitude luminosity increase subsequently observed in both Chile and New Zealand

was the result of the shock wave from the explosion reaching the surface of the collapsed star several hours later.

In fact, the explosion also produced the radioactive elements ^{56}Ni , ^{56}Co and ^{44}Ti , which were turbulently mixed in with the ejected debris and surrounding H-II region in

Figure 5: Theoretical shock wave progression through equatorial ring (Michael et al., 2000)

a manner consistent with widespread

density inhomogeneities in stellar structure (Fransson et al, 2007). Figure 5

depicts the theoretical interaction between the mixed ejecta, the H-II region

and the circumstellar material in the inner (equatorial) ring as the shock wave

continues its outward progression from the site of the explosion (Michael et

al., 2000). This model provides one possible explanation for the formation of

the hot spots, as X-ray imaging has allowed researchers to track the

radioactive decay of ^{56}Ni and ^{56}Co into ^{56}Fe as the shock wave moves

through the circumstellar material that comprises the ring. Under this model,

the inner ring should be uniformly lit as expected once the shock wave fully permeates the inner ring, as the once-distinct spots merge into a single ring. The southwestern brightening of the ring from 2011 to 2013 may therefore be the first sign that the shock wave is beginning to reach the entirety of the inner ring, and that Michael et al. are correct in explaining the hot spots as irregular "fingers" of radioactive ejecta protruding inward.

Furthermore, comparison of the upper limit obtained in this paper for 2013 with the known luminosities of the Crab Pulsar and PSR B0540-69 suggests that if the point source for SN 1987A is in fact a neutron star, is it unlikely a pulsating one (Pesce, 2012). It has also been suggested that the progenitor star was in fact a binary system, which might account for the two outer rings; however, the companion star that did not explode has yet to be detected (Schneider, 2006). Whether the remnant of SN 1987A's progenitor is a neutron star or not, it is increasingly difficult to accept the theory of a binary progenitor in light of the new upper luminosity limit of 4.0×10^{33} ergs/s for 2013. This limit would encompass both the supernova remnant and

the remaining companion star such that the range of possible luminosities for that star become increasingly and implausibly low. The decrease in this limit from 2011 to 2013 therefore constrains the list of possible models regarding progenitor stars further, although the binary system cannot be entirely ruled out.

The decrease in the upper limit from 2011 to 2013 indicates one of two possible scenarios; either the point source itself is decreasing in luminosity, or the continuing expansion of debris away from the explosion site is allowing for more accurate measurements of the hidden compact object that theoretically must be behind it. A decrease in luminosity of the point source would agree with predictions given that the system overall is expanding (Michael et al., 2000); however, it is still impossible to confirm any measurements as directly related to the luminosity of the as-yet-undetected compact light source. Even if the source is indeed fading, it is still possible that the change in the upper limit reflected in these data is the result of debris scattering instead.

Conclusion

Several hours before the explosion of SN 1987A became visible to the human eye, detectors on the northern hemisphere encountered the first non-solar neutrinos ever recorded on Earth. This means there must have been a core collapse to a neutron star, with no further collapse to indicate the formation of a black hole in its place (Arnett et al., 1989). Although the observed burst of neutrinos and standard models of stellar evolution suggest the existence of a compact source inside the remnant debris, it is clear from its peculiar structure and evolution that this supernova makes quite a break with theory. By continuing to monitor the debris expansion, scientists may eventually uncover the elusive compact source located within the remnant. Additionally, continuing to monitor the changing brightness of the ring and its spots has brought significant discoveries regarding the elemental makeup of the circumstellar material, and allowed us to form a more coherent picture of how this most unusual supernova came to explode and how it continues to

evolve. In time, we hope to achieve a better understanding of how these spots form and distinguishing the various phases a supernova like SN 1987a undergoes as it interacts with its environment and evolves both post- and pre-explosion.

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